

Datasheet: Hand-Labeled Road Surface Conditions in New York State Department of Transportation Camera Images

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About

This datasheet serves as data documentation for research being conducted at the University at Albany (State University of New York) and the New York State Department of Transportation to automatically predict weather-related road surface conditions. Specifically, a hand-labeled image dataset (occasionally referred to as simply the “dataset”) is discussed in detail in this document.

Please cite this work if the labeling methods or other details presented in this datasheet are used in your research.

The template for this datasheet is provided by [Gebru et al. \(2021\)](#), and [Cao and Daumé III \(2020\)](#) is used as a reference example of another published datasheet.

Motivation

The questions in this section are primarily intended to encourage dataset creators to clearly articulate their reasons for creating the dataset and to promote transparency about funding

interests. The latter may be particularly relevant for datasets created for research purposes.

1. For what purpose was the dataset created? Was there a specific task in mind? Was there a specific gap that needed to be filled? Please provide a description.

A labeled image dataset is created for the purpose of training machine learning algorithms to predict weather-related road surface conditions based on the camera images. This work is in collaboration with the New York State Department of Transportation (NYSDOT), for which the automated classification of road surface conditions could aid in decision making. All images are hand labeled by human labelers as having one of six classes: 1) severe snow, 2) snow, 3) wet, 4) dry, 5) poor visibility, 6) obstructed. The six classes are established in collaboration with NYSDOT, social scientists, and atmospheric scientists. The images are labeled using a method from social science known as Quantitative Content Analysis (Coe and Scacco, 2017), which is an iterative, systematic hand labeling approach (discussed in question #7). Definitions of each class are discussed in #7 and available at [Sutter et al. \(2025\)](#); this labeling work is also published in [Wirz et al. \(2024\)](#).

2. Who created the dataset (e.g., which team, research group) and on behalf of which entity (e.g., company, institution, organization)?

A research group under co-author Sulia at Atmospheric Sciences Research Center led the creation of the labeled dataset. Co-author Sutter led labeling efforts with contributions from social scientists, co-authors Wirz and Cains, as well as other researchers, co-authors Przybylo, Radford, and Evans.

The images belong to the New York State Department of Transportation (NYSDOT), and the labeled dataset is created for dissertation research. Camera images across New York State (NYS) are available for live viewing at [511ny.org](#) ([NYSDOT, 2025](#)), including approximately 2400 active cameras across the state. The 511NY API is used to retrieve identifying information from each camera, including latitude, longitude, location description, and a URL to the live camera feed. While it is possible to view the cameras in real-time, the NYSDOT does not retain historical recordings nor maintain a static image database. Starting in January 2022, an archive of camera images was established at the xCITE Laboratory ([XCITE, 2025](#)) at the Atmospheric Sciences Research Center, University at Albany. This archive consists of snapshots of all live cameras every five minutes and serves as the data source for our analyses. This archive is discussed in question #7 and the Composition section, questions #21 through #25.

3. Who funded the creation of the dataset? If there is an associated grant, please provide the name of the grantor and the grant name and number.

This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. National Science Foundation under Grant No. RISE-2019758. This work is part of the NSF AI Institute for Research on

Trustworthy AI in Weather, Climate, and Coastal Oceanography (NSF AI2ES).

4. Any other comments?

New York State Mesonet (NYSM; Brotzge et al., 2020) weather observations are also utilized during hand labeling (see questions #7 and #9). The NYSM is a network of high-quality, near-surface weather observations deployed across NYS that capture weather conditions, such as temperature, precipitation, and snow depth. Original funding for the NYS Mesonet buildup was provided by Federal Emergency Management Agency grant FEMA-4085-DR-NY. The continued operation and maintenance of the NYSM is supported by National Mesonet Program, University at Albany, Federal and private grants, and others.

Composition

Dataset creators should read through these questions prior to any data collection and then provide answers once data collection is complete. Most of the questions in this section are intended to provide dataset consumers with the information they need to make informed decisions about using the dataset for their chosen tasks. Some of the questions are designed to elicit information about compliance with the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or comparable regulations in other jurisdictions. Questions that apply only to datasets that relate to people are grouped together at the end of the section. We recommend taking a broad interpretation of whether a dataset relates to people. For example, any dataset containing text that was written by people relates to people.

5. What do the instances that comprise the dataset represent (e.g., documents, photos, people, countries)? Are there multiple types of instances (e.g., movies, users, and ratings; people and interactions between them; nodes and edges)? Please provide a description.

The instances that comprise the dataset represent images taken from roadside camera images. Each instance has a corresponding hand-labeled classification of severe snow, snow, wet, dry, poor visibility, or obstructed, which are discussed in more detail in questions #7 and #9.

6. How many instances are there in total (of each type, if appropriate)?

There are a total of 21,653 labeled instances in total.

7. Does the dataset contain all possible instances or is it a sample (not necessarily random) of instances from a larger set? If the dataset is a sample, then what is the larger set? Is the sample representative of the larger set (e.g., geographic coverage)? If so, please describe how this representativeness was validated/verified. If it is not representative of the larger set,

please describe why not (e.g., to cover a more diverse range of instances, because instances were withheld or unavailable).

Before hand-labeling, the first step is to sample images from the archive. Sampling from the image archive is necessary given that there are approximately 250 million images collected per year. Sampling is performed by first identifying cameras (referred to as “sites”) of interest across NYS; camera sites located at multiple regions throughout NYS are included to incorporate different climate regimes. Sites are also selected considering their proximity to the NYSM (Brotzge et al., 2020), which is utilized during hand-labeling (see question #9). Camera quality is determined qualitatively by considering camera site attributes like lighting, proximity to road, and view of the road. A diverse range of camera qualities are incorporated to ensure a representative dataset for this operational application.

Once a site is identified, a sample of images is collected by selecting dates and times when there was likely to be snow, rain, dry, or poor visibility events using the NYSM observational data. Snowy events are identified by dates with below 0°C temperature measurements, as well as high snow accumulation and high relative humidity, relative to other dates. Measurements of high precipitation accumulation, above 0°C temperatures, and low snow accumulation are used to identify rain events. Dry events are identified based on low accumulated precipitation and low relative humidity. Foggy conditions are identified by high relative humidity measurements with little to no accumulated precipitation or snow. In addition to sampled fog events, the poor visibility class also contains cases where heavy snowfall or rainfall inhibits the ability to see the road.

This sampling technique is used to identify dates and times that may contain each of the six classes, but ultimately, severe snow, snow, and poor visibility conditions are less common. The total number of images and the class distribution within each site varies due to regional constraints (e.g., occurrences of severe snow are less frequent on Long Island compared to Buffalo) as well as camera-specific constraints (e.g., some sites have a large number of obstructed images). Some sites are sampled more heavily in an effort to find more cases of a less frequent class (e.g., poor visibility or severe snow). In contrast, other sites contain a small number of images because they are sampled for the purpose of increasing the variability of sites within a given class. Given the sampling considerations discussed, out of the 45 sites, 32 sites contained approximately 500 images, five sites contained 1000 images, two sites contain approximately 200 each, and six sites contain under 40 images.

The final hand-labeled dataset (Figure 1) contains a total 21,653 images, and the class distribution is a consequence of the actual road surface conditions that were present in the set of sampled images, as determined by hand labeling. Overall, images from 182 unique dates are labeled, primarily ranging from January 2022 to March 2023. Only winter months are used because snow events are a primary focus of the NYSDOT. The next section includes details about each of the classes and the image labeling process.

8. What data does each instance consist of? “Raw” data (e.g., unprocessed text or images) or features? In either case, please provide a description.

Each instance includes a path to an unprocessed image from the image archive (see #2 and #7) and its corresponding hand-labeled classification (see #9 and Figure 1).

9. Is there a label or target associated with each instance? If so, please provide a description.

From the set of sampled images (see #7), a label of severe snow, snow, wet, dry, poor visibility, or obstructed is assigned to each instance. Definitions of each class and the systematic hand labeling methods employed are described below, but more details are available at [Sutter et al. \(2025\)](#) and [Wirz et al. \(2024\)](#).

Labeling is a time-consuming and detailed process that is made more difficult by the variety of image backgrounds and range of camera quality. Additionally, establishing the definitions of road surface condition classes is an iterative process. Multiple classification schemes are tested ranging from using three broad classes of snow, wet, and dry, to using more granular classes, such as using four levels of severity for snow. However, the final six classes are ultimately selected based on a combination of conversations with the NYSDOT and group work consisting of six human labelers following a process known as quantitative content analysis (QCA; [Coe and Scacco, 2017](#)).

QCA is a systematic method for labeling data in a way that is replicable, meaning that the labeling approach can be applied to new data (e.g., new cameras, new states, etc.), and reproducible, meaning that a different labeler can achieve the same or very similar results by using the same labeling scheme on the same images ([Wirz et al., 2024](#)). This is done through careful documentation of decisions and classification definitions in a document referred to as the labeling “codebook”. The codebook is validated through inter-coder reliability (ICR) trials, which is a means to test the efficacy of the codebook by measuring consistency across multiple independent human labelers. A trial is conducted by having each member of the labeling group all label the same small sample (e.g., 50) of images that contain all six classes. ICR can be measured by various metrics, each with their own strengths and weaknesses ([Wirz et al., 2024](#)). This study uses the Krippendorff alpha (KA) measure ([Hayes and Krippendorff, 2007](#)) to assess the consistency within the labeling group as it works well for categorical data, accommodates any number of coders, and allows for unlabeled data ([Wirz et al., 2024](#)). The KA standard for ICR is 0.80 or greater. If this standard is not met, the group convenes to identify areas of discrepancy, adjusts the codebook accordingly, and then conducts another trial. The 6-person labeling group (authors of this paper including Sutter, Wirz, Przybylo, Cains, Radford, Evans) for this project achieved the reliability goal on the fourth trial, with a KA measure of 0.888. The codebook and data from the reliability trials, including the images used for the trials and the results and statistics, can be found in [Sutter et al. \(2025\)](#).

The QCA method provides four major benefits, the first being that multiple labelers are able to work independently to produce more labeled images, taking a “divide and conquer” approach. Second, when labeling is done in different batches, sometimes months apart, the codebook documentation provides a way to maintain consistency through time. This is especially important because the variety of image locations, proximity to the road, roadway lighting, camera quality, etc., can make labeling a tedious task. A third benefit is that the codebook encourages clear communication and collaboration with the intended end-user, the

NYSDOT. Lastly, the codebook enables replicability because it provides a framework that can be followed in the future to add more labeled data, whether that is to include more labeled data from NYS or expanding to an entirely new state. Labeling data using the QCA method leads to clear documentation of what defines each class (i.e., the “codebook”) and ultimately results in the creation of a well-documented and consistent dataset that is used to train the ML models.

The labeled classes are shown in Figure 1. Detailed definitions of each of these classes for labeling purposes are developed in collaboration with NYSDOT and based on what is reasonably determined in images. For each image, the corresponding weather observational data are collected from the NYSM; The NYSM data are available to aid in decision making during labeling, especially under borderline circumstances (e.g., dry vs. wet) and poor lighting.

Six Classes			Site Quality
<p>Severe snow - 1,527</p>			
<p>Dry - 7,600</p>			

Figure 1: (Left) Examples of labeled classes (Right) Examples of high- and low- quality sites

The first four classes - severe snow, snow, wet, and dry - align with the classes listed in the Winter Travel Advisory (NYSDOT, 2023) and the winter road conditions that the NYSDOT uses for 511ny.org/map (NYSDOT, 2025). Severe snow is the classification when pavement is not visible (or minimally visible) in wheel paths, or there are no wheel paths within the snow/slush build-up. Snow is the classification when pavement is visible in wheel paths within the snow/slush, including areas with wind-blown snow. Wet is the classification when the segment is wet with liquid water from rain or fully melted snow, and dry is the classification when the entire length of the segment appears clear and dry.

Poor visibility is the classification when either the road is not visible at all or the road is slightly visible, but the road surface condition is not apparent due to weather-related low visibility. Poor visibility proves to be a difficult class - both for labeling and for the

model to predict - because it is associated with multiple types of weather, such as dense fog, heavy rain, or blizzard-like conditions. However, poor visibility is an important class to distinguish for two reasons. Firstly, it shows up often enough during the codebook iterative development process. Secondly, poor visibility creates dangerous driving conditions; a study by Call et al. (2018) found that restricted visibility is associated with 40% of multi-vehicle crashes. The five weather-related classes are labeled following the foundational codebook from Sutter et al. (2025), which includes further details, rules, and examples.

The obstructed class is generally a non-weather-related class, such as problems with the camera (e.g., ice accumulation on the entire lens) or image (e.g., a blank image). This class is reserved for extreme circumstances where road surface conditions cannot be assessed solely due to camera or image problems. There are many reasons for obstructions, such as the image being too dark, over-exposed, not facing the road, or the camera lens being compromised. Obstructions are labeled following the addendum codebook from Sutter et al. (2025).

10. Is any information missing from individual instances? If so, please provide a description, explaining why this information is missing (e.g., because it was unavailable). This does not include intentionally removed information, but might include, e.g., redacted text.

No information is missing from individual instances.

11. Are relationships between individual instances made explicit (e.g., users' movie ratings, social network links)? If so, please describe how these relationships are made explicit.

The only relationships between instances are location (latitude and longitude) which are available for each instance.

12. Are there recommended data splits (e.g., training, development/validation, testing)? If so, please provide a description of these splits, explaining the rationale behind them.

Generalizability is crucial for this application with the NYSDOT because creating a labeled dataset for training models is a manual and time-consuming process. Extensive time and resources (human labelers) would be needed to label images from all 2400 camera sites, and even so, camera sites may be added and or change in the future. Thus, the goal is to build a model that can make accurate predictions on all cameras despite only being trained on a small subset of labeled cameras.

Generalizability is reflected in the data-splitting process by assigning all observations from a single site to the same fold. With 45 unique sites and six folds, this means that there are approximately 7-8 camera sites per fold. This splitting method is referred to as "site-specific split" because the training, validation, and testing datasets contain unique camera sites; there are no overlapping cameras between folds (Figure 2, left).

For the site-specific split, the decision about which sites belong to which fold is made by creating combinations of sites such that the resulting six folds contain roughly the same

Figure 2: **Splitting methods.** A demonstration of the two data splitting methods is shown using an example of two sites, A and B, and two Folds, where one is training data and the other is validation data. The site-specific method is the focus of this study because, given the application, models should be assessed on sites it has not seen in training.

amount of higher quality versus lower quality sites, and approximately the same class distribution (see question #7). This was done by first separating the sites into two groups, higher quality cameras (30 sites) and lower quality cameras (15 sites), assigning folds randomly to each site, observing the class distribution count, and then refining the fold assignments iteratively until each fold had approximately the same representation of quality and class.

The site-specific split is the primary data splitting method because it addresses operational goals of generalizability. However, an alternative split method, referred to as the “shuffle split”, can be investigated where each fold contains samples from all 45 camera sites; every site is represented in every fold (Figure 2, right). Regardless of splitting technique, no single image appears more than once in the entire dataset. While the site-specific split is the focus, the shuffle split method may be used in supplementary experiments to emphasize decisions and methods that improve generalizability.

Certain parts of NYS, like Long Island, have a limited number of snow and severe snow events due to its warmer climate. Thus, autocorrelation is a problem in the shuffle-split dataset because, with a limited number of samples from a given class at a given site, images from the same weather event may be included in the training, validation, and testing datasets. However, the site-specific split results in a strict difference between images in training, validation, and test datasets because they contain completely different camera sites, and thus, completely different road surface scenes. This further emphasizes the importance of the site-specific split method; when each fold has unique sites, the concern of training and validating on correlated images is removed.

13. Are there any errors, sources of noise, or redundancies in the dataset? If so, please provide a description.

There are occurrences when live cameras become unavailable, in which case, the image displays a blank white image with the text “No live camera feed at this time”. These instances, which are labeled as “obstructed”, are included in the dataset to be inclusive of occurrences that happen in real-world operations.

14. Is the dataset self-contained, or does it link to or otherwise rely on external resources (e.g.,

websites, tweets, other datasets)? If it links to or relies on external resources, a) are there guarantees that they will exist, and remain constant, over time; b) are there official archival versions of the complete dataset (i.e., including the external resources as they existed at the time the dataset was created); c) are there any restrictions (e.g., licenses, fees) associated with any of the external resources that might apply to a dataset consumer? Please provide descriptions of all external resources and any restrictions associated with them, as well as links or other access points, as appropriate.

The dataset relies on the NYSDOT through the external website 511ny.org (NYSDOT, 2025). a) To the best of our knowledge, this resource will continue to exist, although more cameras may be added. b) There is no official archive of this dataset. c) The live camera data is free and publicly available at 511ny.org, following their data policy.

15. Does the dataset contain data that might be considered confidential (e.g., data that is protected by legal privilege or by doctor patient confidentiality, data that includes the content of individuals' non-public communications)? If so, please provide a description.

The labeled data is not confidential.

16. Does the dataset contain data that, if viewed directly, might be offensive, insulting, threatening, or might otherwise cause anxiety? If so, please describe why.

Given that the camera feeds are on the roadways, there may be accidents or other incidents shown.

17. Does the dataset identify any subpopulations (e.g., by age, gender)? If so, please describe how these subpopulations are identified and provide a description of their respective distributions within the dataset.

Not applicable.

18. Is it possible to identify individuals (i.e., one or more natural persons), either directly or indirectly (i.e., in combination with other data) from the dataset? If so, please describe how.

License plates are generally not identifiable nor legible in the images, although may be possible.

19. Does the dataset contain data that might be considered sensitive in any way (e.g., data that reveals race or ethnic origins, sexual orientations, religious beliefs, political opinions or union memberships, or locations; financial or health data; biometric or genetic data; forms of government identification, such as social security numbers; criminal history)

No.

20. Any other comments?

None.

Collection Process

As with the questions in the previous section, dataset creators should read through these questions prior to any data collection to flag potential issues and then provide answers once collection is complete. In addition to the goals outlined in the previous section, the questions in this section are designed to elicit information that may help researchers and practitioners to create alternative datasets with similar characteristics. Again, questions that apply only to datasets that relate to people are grouped together at the end of the section.

21. How was the data associated with each instance acquired? Was the data directly observable (e.g., raw text, movie ratings), reported by subjects (e.g., survey responses), or indirectly inferred/derived from other data (e.g., part-of-speech tags, model-based guesses for age or language)? If the data was reported by subjects or indirectly inferred/derived from other data, was the data validated/verified? If so, please describe how.

Each instance is directly observable from the live data source at 511ny.org ([NYSDOT, 2025](#)), which is saved in the image archive and is subsequently hand-labeled by human labelers as described in the Composition section (see questions #7 and #9).

22. What mechanisms or procedures were used to collect the data (e.g., hardware apparatuses or sensors, manual human curation, software programs, software APIs)? How were these mechanisms or procedures validated?

The data is collected using the 511ny.org ([NYSDOT, 2025](#)) REST API, which provides information on each camera, such as its latitude, longitude, and a URL to the live camera feed. After receiving permission from the NYSDOT to build an image archive, a cron job scheduler is set up to save a snapshot of all camera images every five minutes.

23. If the dataset is a sample from a larger set, what was the sampling strategy (e.g., deterministic, probabilistic with specific sampling probabilities)?

The live camera feed at 511ny.org offers live video and real-time imagery from roadside cameras, which update as frequently as every 30 seconds. The archive stores images every five minutes, which is a timeframe that strikes a balance between capturing sudden changes

in road conditions and minimizing data storage concerns.

24. Who was involved in the data collection process (e.g., students, crowdworkers, contractors) and how were they compensated (e.g., how much were crowdworkers paid)?

Co-author Sutter (graduate student, funded as a research assistant through the Research Foundation at SUNY) wrote the script to fetch an image from each camera site given the URLs provided by the API, and led the data labeling process. The cron job scheduler was established by co-author Sulia (faculty and Associate Director) and Arnoldas Kurbanovas (computing supervisor), both employed at the University at Albany and the Research Foundation at SUNY.

25. Over what timeframe was the data collected? Does this timeframe match the creation timeframe of the data associated with the instances (e.g., recent crawl of old news articles)? If not, please describe the timeframe in which the data associated with the instances was created.

The data archive is ongoing and began in January 2022.

26. Were any ethical review processes conducted (e.g., by an institutional review board)? If so, please provide a description of these review processes, including the outcomes, as well as a link or other access point to any supporting documentation.

No ethical review processes were conducted.

27. Did you collect the data from the individuals in question directly, or obtain it via third parties or other sources (e.g., websites)?

Not applicable.

28. Were the individuals in question notified about the data collection? If so, please describe (or show with screenshots or other information) how notice was provided, and provide a link or other access point to, or otherwise reproduce, the exact language of the notification itself.

Not applicable.

29. Did the individuals in question consent to the collection and use of their data? If so, please describe (or show with screenshots or other information) how consent was requested and provided, and provide a link or other access point to, or otherwise reproduce, the exact language to which the individuals consented.

Not applicable.

30. If consent was obtained, were the consenting individuals provided with a mechanism to revoke their consent in the future or for certain uses? If so, please provide a description, as well as a link or other access point to the mechanism (if appropriate).

Not applicable.

31. Has an analysis of the potential impact of the dataset and its use on data subjects (e.g., a data protection impact analysis) been conducted? If so, please provide a description of this analysis, including the outcomes, as well as a link or other access point to any supporting documentation.

Not applicable.

32. Any other comments?

None.

Preprocessing/cleaning/labeling

Dataset creators should read through these questions prior to any preprocessing, cleaning, or labeling and then provide answers once these tasks are complete. The questions in this section are intended to provide dataset consumers with the information they need to determine whether the “raw” data has been processed in ways that are compatible with their chosen tasks. For example, text that has been converted into a “bag-of-words” is not suitable for tasks involving word order.

33. Was any preprocessing/cleaning/labeling of the data done (e.g., discretization or bucketing, tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, SIFT feature extraction, removal of instances, processing of missing values)? If so, please provide a description. If not, you may skip the remaining questions in this section.

The images in this labeled dataset are not preprocessed or cleaned. Labeling of the image data is performed by human labelers following the processes as described in the Composition section (see questions #7 and #9).

34. Was the “raw” data saved in addition to the preprocessed/cleaned/labeled data (e.g., to support unanticipated future uses)? If so, please provide a link or other access point to the “raw” data.

Not applicable; un-processed archived image data is used to label the images.

35. Is the software that was used to preprocess/clean/label the data available? If so, please provide a link or other access point.

No software is available; the hand labeling was performed by humans to label the dataset (see questions #7 and #9), and the corresponding codebook and procedure is available at [Sutter et al. \(2025\)](#).

36. Any other comments?

None.

Uses

The questions in this section are intended to encourage dataset creators to reflect on the tasks for which the dataset should and should not be used. By explicitly highlighting these tasks, dataset creators can help dataset consumers to make informed decisions, thereby avoiding potential risks or harms.

37. Has the dataset been used for any tasks already? If so, please provide a description.

The dataset is being used for machine learning classification models that are in development at the University at Albany. The purpose of these models is to automatically classify weather-related road surface conditions based on the camera image data.

38. Is there a repository that links to any or all papers or systems that use the dataset? If so, please provide a link or other access point.

No.

39. What (other) tasks could the dataset be used for?

This dataset could be used for any task that relates to the classification of weather-related road surface conditions. While other tasks could be considered (e.g., traffic detection, weather conditions), more labeling would need to be performed accordingly.

40. Is there anything about the composition of the dataset or the way it was collected and preprocessed/cleaned/labeled that might impact future uses? For example, is there anything that a dataset consumer might need to know to avoid uses that could result in unfair treatment

of individuals or groups (e.g., stereotyping, quality of service issues) or other risks or harms (e.g., legal risks, financial harms)? If so, please provide a description. Is there anything a dataset consumer could do to mitigate these risks or harms?

No.

41. Are there tasks for which the dataset should not be used? If so, please provide a description.

Given that the dataset is labeled based on weather-related road surface conditions, tasks that are outside of that scope would not be appropriate without relabeling the data.

42. Any other comments?

None.

Distribution

Dataset creators should provide answers to these questions prior to distributing the dataset either internally within the entity on behalf of which the dataset was created or externally to third parties.

43. Will the dataset be distributed to third parties outside of the entity (e.g., company, institution, organization) on behalf of which the dataset was created? If so, please provide a description.

The dataset is currently private and will only be distributed to the partners and collaborators of this funded project within the terms of the contract.

44. How will the dataset be distributed (e.g., tarball on website, API, GitHub)? Does the dataset have a digital object identifier (DOI)?

The dataset will be distributed as a csv file that contains paths the archive images and their corresponding labels. The dataset does not have a DOI currently but will have one prior to data distribution.

45. When will the dataset be distributed?

The dataset will be distributed according to the terms of the contract and in collaboration with the NYSDOT.

46. Will the dataset be distributed under a copyright or other intellectual property (IP) license, and/or under applicable terms of use (ToU)? If so, please describe this license and/or ToU, and provide a link or other access point to, or otherwise reproduce, any relevant licensing terms or ToU, as well as any fees associated with these restrictions.

The underlying images are property of the New York State Department of Transportation, and the labeled classifications are property of The Research Foundation through NSF Funding (see question #3.)

47. Have any third parties imposed IP-based or other restrictions on the data associated with the instances? If so, please describe these restrictions, and provide a link or other access point to, or otherwise reproduce, any relevant licensing terms, as well as any fees associated with these restrictions.

The purposes for the data archive are for this project only and any future work by researchers outside of this author list must receive permission from the NYSDOT.

48. Do any export controls or other regulatory restrictions apply to the dataset or to individual instances? If so, please describe these restrictions, and provide a link or other access point to, or otherwise reproduce, any supporting documentation.

See above, #47.

49. Any other comments?

While the dataset is private, the purpose of this datasheet is to provide transparent documentation of how the labeled image dataset is developed so that other groups can replicate this work using their relevant datasets.

Maintenance

As with the questions in the previous section, dataset creators should provide answers to these questions prior to distributing the dataset. The questions in this section are intended to encourage dataset creators to plan for dataset maintenance and communicate this plan to dataset consumers.

50. Who will be supporting/hosting/maintaining the dataset?

The dataset will be hosted by the xCITE laboratory in the Atmospheric Sciences Research Center at the University at Albany ([XCITE, 2025](#)).

51. How can the owner/curator/manager of the dataset be contacted (e.g., email address)?

The owners of the dataset can be contacted via email: Carly Sutter (csutter@albany.edu) and Kara Sulia (ksulia@albany.edu)

52. Is there an erratum? If so, please provide a link or other access point.

No.

53. Will the dataset be updated (e.g., to correct labeling errors, add new instances, delete instances)? If so, please describe how often, by whom, and how updates will be communicated to dataset consumers (e.g., mailing list, GitHub)?

Updates to the dataset in the future may include additional labeled data or changed labels. Should the dataset become publicly available, any updates will be communicated by providing an updated version of the labeled dataset on the host site.

54. If the dataset relates to people, are there applicable limits on the retention of the data associated with the instances (e.g., were the individuals in question told that their data would be retained for a fixed period of time and then deleted)? If so, please describe these limits and explain how they will be enforced.

Not applicable.

55. Will older versions of the dataset continue to be supported/hosted/maintained? If so, please describe how. If not, please describe how its obsolescence will be communicated to dataset consumers.

Should the dataset become publicly available, all older versions of the data will remain accessible.

56. If others want to extend/augment/build on/contribute to the dataset, is there a mechanism for them to do so? If so, please provide a description. Will these contributions be validated/verified? If so, please describe how. If not, why not? Is there a process for communicating/distributing these contributions to dataset consumers? If so, please provide a description.

Should the dataset become publicly available, there will not be a mechanism for others outside of the research team to extend/augment/build on/contribute to the dataset.

57. Any other comments?

None.

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